

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

CAESAREAN SECTION INDICATIONS AND OUTCOMES AT A PUBLIC HOSPITAL IN LAGOS, NIGERIA: A 2-YEAR REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Caesarean delivery is one of the most commonly performed surgical procedures in obstetrics. This study was conducted to determine the caesarean section rate and indications for caesarean section at the study centre.

Methods: An institutional-based retrospective descriptive study of all caesarean sections with completed data in the case notes using a structured questionnaire to collect data. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 22 (SPSS) was used. A two-sided P-value, that is, $p < 0.05$, was considered statistically significant.

Results: During the study period, there were 4100 deliveries of which 1811 were caesarean sections giving a caesarean section rate of 44%. The commonest indication for primary caesarean section was cephalopelvic disproportion while a previous caesarean section was the commonest for elective caesarean section.

Conclusions: The caesarean section in this study triples the recommended upper limit by the World Health Organisation. Ensuring the woman merit the primary caesarean section, appropriate case selection for VBAC to reduce caesarean section, and good government policy to avoid incessant health care provider industrial action will contribute to the reduction in the caesarean section.

Keywords: Caesarean section, rate, incidence, indications, Lagos, pregnant women

Introduction

A Caesarean section is a surgical procedure that involves incisions made through a mother's abdomen (laparotomy) and uterus (hysterotomy) to deliver one or more fetuses, placenta and membranes or to remove a dead fetus after the age of viability.^{1,2}

The rise in unnecessary caesarean sections, which offer no additional benefits to maternal and perinatal outcomes, is a significant public concern. The World Health Organization

recommends a caesarean delivery rate of 10-15% in industrialized and developing countries alike.³ Countries with a caesarean section rate of less than 5% suffer from inadequate or absent necessary interventions, while those with a rate greater than 15% are subjecting women to unnecessary interventions.⁴

Over two decades ago, the widespread and increasing proportion of caesarean sections was in the limelight, with various interventions suggested, however no consensus on the appropriate CSR.⁵

Despite the traditional aversion of Nigerian women towards caesarean delivery because of cultural or religious beliefs, the caesarean section rate in Nigerian teaching hospitals varies. It is important to note that caesarean sections are a necessary medical procedure for certain obstetric indications including previous caesarean section, dystocia, hypertensive disease, premature rupture of the membrane, malposition, malpresentation, cephalopelvic disproportion, and multiple pregnancies.¹ In addition, non-obstetric indications such as fear of litigation, mental fatigue of physician, financial gain, precious baby sentiment, assisted conception, maternal aversion to pain, and maternal requests have also been recorded.^{6,7,8} While repeat caesarean section is the leading cause of elective caesarean sections, cephalopelvic disproportion is the leading cause of the emergency in most Nigerian studies.^{7,8}

This study was conducted as part of the clinical audit by the quality assurance team to determine the caesarean section rate and indications for a caesarean section in the study Centre. In addition, to evaluate the outcome of 1811 caesarean deliveries over the study period and compare the outcomes of the primary caesarean section to the previous caesarean section, to know the causes of the upsurge, and to provide objective data for interventions aimed at reducing unnecessary caesarean sections in the study Centre.

Materials and Methods

Study design

This study aimed to determine the rate and indications for caesarean section at the Study Centre. It was a retrospective study of all caesarean sections performed during the study period at the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department of the Mother and Child Care, Gbaja, Surulere.

Study population

The study population consisted of 1,393 case notes with complete information out of 1,811 women who underwent a caesarean section during the study period.

Inclusion criteria

All patients who underwent Caesarean section at this facility with complete data were included.

Exclusion criteria

All patients who underwent a Caesarean section in this facility, along with those who did not, but have incomplete data in their case notes.

Data/Sample Collection

The data was collected from the case notes of patients who underwent caesarean section procedures, the labour ward records, delivery register, theatre records, and neonatal unit records. A pre-designed form extracted crucial details such as patient demographics, type of caesarean section, anesthesia type, maternal and fetal outcomes, duration of hospital stay, and total number of deliveries during the period.

Data Analysis

The data collected for the study were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 22.0 (Chicago, Illinois, USA). Categorical variables were described using absolute numbers and simple percentages, while quantitative variables were described using appropriate measures of central tendency (mean, median) and measures of dispersion (range, standard deviation). To determine the association between caesarean section and perinatal mortality, Pearson's coefficient of correlation and student's t-test were used. A P-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

During the study period, 1811 women had a caesarean section. However, only 1393 case notes were involved in the study as they had complete information. Tables 1 & 2 present the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of two distinct study groups: the previous CS group (38%), consisting of individuals with a history of cesarean sections, and the primary CS group (62%), comprising those without such a history.

There was a significant difference in the primary cesarean section (CS) rate between two groups in the 20-29 age distribution ($p = 0.001$). The primary CS group had a higher CS rate of 51.1% in this age group, while the previous CS group had a lower rate of 21.7%.

The mean age of the primary CS group was 29.5 ± 5.0 years, which was younger than the previous CS group with a mean age of 32.8 ± 4.2 years.

There was no statistically significant difference between marital status and occupation between the two groups. ($P > 0.05$).

The majority of women with previous CS were booked (98%) for the ANC. Proportions of unbooked patients were higher among the primary CS than the previous CS group, and the booking status, parity, gestational age and Pre-op PCV

were statistically significant among the two groups. ($P < 0.5$).

The Estimated Blood Loss, Post-op PCV and Temperature (48 hours post-op) were not statistically significantly different between the two groups.

Table 3: shows the indications for caesarean section in this study, the types of anaesthesia, postoperative antibiotics, and surgical site infection among the two groups. Maternal indications for caesarean section accounted for about 84% while foetal indications accounted for 16%. The leading causes of maternal indication were Previous Caesarean section (38%), Cephalopelvic disproportion in 23.4%, and failed VBAC (7.4%) while 37.5% of women in the primary group indicated a failure to progress (CPD + Obstructed Labour) as a reason for embarking on Caesarean Section. There is a statistically significant difference between the two groups of women ($P < 0.05$). Spinal anaesthesia was largely mentioned as the type of anaesthesia done by women in both groups. No statistically significant difference between the two groups of women ($P > 0.05$). Other parameters evaluated are post-op antibiotics and surgical site infection which indicated that both are the same for the women with previous experience of Caesarean Section and those who are in the primary group, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups of women ($P > 0.05$).

No gender difference in terms of the number of fetal recorded during the Caesarean Section, and no statistically significant to CS and those with previous experience ($P > 0.05$) while neonatal and foetal outcomes of women in the primary group are statistically significantly different from those with previous experience of Caesarean Section ($P < 0.05$).

Apgar Score 1 of women in the primary group and those with previous experience of caesarean section were statistically significantly different while foetal weight and Apgar score 5 at birth in the two groups of women are insignificant ($P > 0.05$).

Discussion

The caesarean section rate over the study period was 44.2%. This was rather very high despite known strong aversion of Nigerian women to this procedure. It was higher than 11% found in a

study done in Sokoto⁹, 18% in Jos¹⁰, 19.9% in Ado-Ekiti¹¹, 21.4% in Abuja¹², 23.1% in Sagamu¹³, 28.6% in Yenagoa¹⁴, 40.8% in Ogbomoso¹⁵, 24.1% in Pakistan¹⁵, a developing country like Nigeria and it's about 3 folds of the maximum recommended rate of 10-15% by the WHO for the developing countries⁴. This finding was similar to the study conducted by Allagoa et.al 2020⁷, where 959 women out of 2263 deliveries had caesarean sections giving the Caesarean section rate (CSR) of 42.4%⁷. The CSR in urban settlements in Nigeria ranges from 11.3% to 42.4%.⁵⁻¹⁵ The frequency of caesarean section depends on the sociodemographic pattern, obstetrics population, referral role of the hospital, availability of skilled birth attendants, previous caesarean section, departmental policies regarding the management of foetal distress, breech, cephalopelvic disproportion and previous caesarean section, medicolegal aspects and consideration for the maternal wish¹⁵.

In this study, the referral role of this study Centre, which served the primary health care centres, and other general hospitals, spilt over patients from the adjoining Federal tertiary hospital when there's short of bed space during intermittent or inadvertent health care workers industrial strike actions made most of their patients booked earlier with the facility, thus hike the rate of previous CS group seen in the study. The majority of the women who had caesarean sections were booked patients 95.8%. Cephalopelvic disproportion is the commonest indication for emergency caesarean section and is usually more common among un-booked patients¹⁵. However, in this study, the majority of women in both the primary CS group and the previous CS group were booked. Most of them had primarily booked in either the primary health care or tertiary hospital before referral or they self-referred themselves due to ongoing industrial strikes. Some were already booked in a general hospital but went to Traditional Birth Attendance (TBA) for labour and were pushed out when complications occurred (cephalopelvic disproportion, obstructed labour, uterine rupture with intrauterine foetal demise). The CSR among women with the age category 20-29years was 39.9%, like the findings in other studies^{16,17} (Igberase et.al 50.1%, Geldam et.al 52.8% et.al.). The modal age group in the study was 30-39 years with CSR of 55.7%, unlike other

studies which had the modal age group of 20-29years.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables		Total (1393) n %	Primary: 861 (n %)	Previous: 532 (n %)	Chi-square / T-test	P-value
Age	<20years	13 (0.9)	12 (1.4)	1 (0.2)		
	20 - 29years	555 (39.9)	440 (51.1)	115 (21.7)	128.7	0.000
	30 - 39years	776 (55.7)	385 (44.7)	391 (73.6)		
	40years and above	48 (3.4)	24 (2.8)	24 (4.5)		
	Mean \pm SD		29.5 \pm 5.0	32.8 \pm 4.2	-12.48	0.00
Marital Status	Single	4 (0.3)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.2)		
	Married	1386 (99.6)	856 (99.4)	530 (99.8)	1.53	0.68
	Engaged	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)		
	Divorced	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)		
Occupation	Professional (Accounting Banker/Lawyer)	16 (1.1)	7 (0.8)	9 (1.7)		
	Business	13 (0.9)	5 (0.6)	8 (1.5)		
	Trading	741 (53.2)	447 (51.5)	294 (55.3)		
	Civil Servant	141 (10.1)	90 (10.5)	51 (9.6)	8.68	0.28
	Artisan	50 (3.6)	32 (3.7)	18 (3.4)		
	Student /Corper	32 (2.3)	23 (2.7)	9 (1.7)		
	Housewife	387 (27.8)	249 (28.9)	138 (25.9)		

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables		Total (1393) n %	Primary (n %)	Previous (n %)	Chi-square / T-test	P-value
Booking Status	Booked	1335 (95.8)	812 (94.3)	523 (98.3)	13.18	0.000
	Unbooked	58 (4.2)	49 (5.7)	9 (1.7)		
Parity	1	661 (48.4)	605 (72.2)	56 (10.6)		
	2	417 (30.5)	163 (19.5)	254 (48.1)	509.42	0.00
	3	228 (16.7)	51 (6.1)	177 (33.5)		
	4 and above	60 (4.4)	19 (2.3)	41 (7.8)		
	Modal parity		1			
Gestational Age			38.4 \pm 1.9	37.6 \pm 1.5	7.82	0.00
Estimated Blood Loss			464.1 \pm 259.6	469.9 \pm 279.9	-0.39	0.70
Pre-op PCV			33.7 \pm 3.3	33.3 \pm 2.7	2.05	0.04
Post-op PCV			30.2 \pm 3.5	30.4 \pm 3.1	-1.07	0.28
Temperature (48hours post-op)			36.6 \pm 1.4	36.6 \pm 0.5	-0.79	0.43

Table 3: Overview of Maternal Caesarean Section

Variables		Total (1393) n %	Primary (n %)	Previous (n %)	Chi-square / T-test	P-value
Indication for Caesarean Section	Previous CS only	395 (36.9)	0 (0.0)	395 (74.2)		
	Abnormal Doppler finding	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)		
	Antepartum haemorrhage	21 (1.5)	21 (2.4)	0 (0.0)		
	Foetal Macrosomia	36 (2.6)	36 (4.2)	0 (0.0)		
	Foetal Distress	103 (7.5)	103 (12.0)	0 (0.0)		
	Failure to progress (CPD + Obstructed Labour)	323 (23.4)	323 (37.5)	0 (0.0)	1346.04	0.00
	Eclampsia (severe pre-eclampsia)	55 (4.0)	55 (6.4)	0 (0.0)		
	Previous Myomectomy	11 (0.8)	11 (1.3)	0 (0.0)		
	Failed Induction	62 (4.5)	62 (7.2)	0 (0.0)		
	Uterine Fibroid	6 (0.4)	6 (0.7)	0 (0.0)		
	Elderly / Older Primigravida	15 (1.1)	15 (1.7)	0 (0.0)		
	IUFD with previous CS + Inadequate pelvis	35 (2.5)	0 (0)	35 (6.6)		
	Foetal Malpresentation/Malposition	80 (5.8)	80 (9.3)	0 (0.0)		
	Failed VBAC	102 (7.4)	0(0)	102 (19.2)		
	Delayed 2nd Stage	16 (1.2)	16 (1.9)	0 (0.0)		
	Others(GDM,HBSS)	3 (0.2)	3 (0.3)	0 (0.0)		
Type of Anaesthesia	Spinal	1340 (96.3)	824 (95.7)	516 (97.4)	2.55	0.11
	General	51 (3.7)	37 (4.3)	14 (2.6)		
Post-op Antibiotics	Augmentin	261 (18.8)	167 (19.4)	94 (17.7)		
	Ceftriazone	181 (13.0)	121 (14.1)	60 (11.3)		
	Cepodox	2 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.2)		
	Fortsporine	3 (0.2)	3 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	9.32	0.23
	Mesporin	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.2)		
	Oxazone	22 (1.6)	16 (1.9)	6 (1.1)		
	Salbactam	921 (66.2)	551 (64.1)	370 (69.5)		
	Zinacef	1 (0.1)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)		
Surgical Site Infection	Yes	50 (3.6)	36 (4.2)	14 (2.6)	2.28	0.13
	No	1343 (96.4)	825 (95.8)	518 (97.4)		

Table 4: Foetal Characteristics after Caesarean Section

Variables		Total (1393) n %	Primary (n %)	Previous (n %)	Chi-square / T-test	P-value
Foetal Sex	Male	660 (47.7)	421 (49.2)	239 (45.2)	2.1	0.15
	Female	725 (52.3)	435 (50.8)	290 (54.8)		
Neonatal	Yes	860 (62.6)	559 (65.7)	301 (57.7)	8.9	0.002
	No	513 (37.4)	292 (34.3)	221 (42.3)		
Foetal Outcome	Alive	1278 (91.7)	774 (89.9)	504 (94.7)	10.18	0.001
	Dead	115 (8.3)	87 (10.1)	28 (5.3)		
Foetal Weight (kg)			3.2 ± 0.6	3.2 ± 0.5	-0.57	0.57
APGAR 1			7.3 ± 1.1	7.4 ± 1.0	-2.23	0.03
APGAR 5			8.8 ± 0.9	8.9 ± 0.9	-1.77	0.08

The CSR in Primigravida of 48.4% was higher than the 25% and 36.7% reported in Sagamu¹³ and Maiduguri¹⁷ respectively. This was unacceptably high and posed serious implications for their future reproductive careers. The majority of women in this study were married traders in their first pregnancy. In this study, the maternal indication accounted for 80% of the indication for CS, among which cephalopelvic disproportion and previous CS topped the list with 36.9% and 23.4% respectively. This is like reports from other studies in other parts of Nigeria and other developing countries,^{13,17,18}. In this study, repeat caesarean section was done for 7.2% of women with failed vagina birth after CS. Trials of labour under close monitoring in carefully selected patients have been shown to result in normal delivery in 64.8- 86% of patients¹⁷. Like the study from Ethiopia, foetal distress accounted for 7.5% of foetal indications for CS. This was lower than 11.6% in Geldam, and 18% in Zaire.¹⁷. This lower value may be related to the availability of continuous electronic foetal monitoring during labour in the study Centre. However, foetal scalp sampling was not available.

Post-operative antibiotics commonly used were Sulbactam and there was no reflection on the form of caesarean section and surgical site infection rate. Perinatal outcome and APGAR score in 1 minute were statistically significant for the 2 groups. This implied that prompt intervention aided in securing the life of the fetus and its hypoxia-scoring guide at 1 minute of life. Although WHO recommended CSR within 10-15%, however, it's important to grant all women timely access to caesarean section when critical to

save the lives of the mother and foetus, irrespective of the CSR of the population in focus³.

Caregivers need to be educated on the need for prompt referral and the patient should be properly evaluated and merit primary surgery irrespective of the CSR for the developing or developed population.

Future studies should be prospective for the ease of complete data and thorough analysis.

Limitation

This is a retrospective study with difficulty in retrieving some case notes, as well as missing data, this reduced sample size and may have an impact on the validity and causality of the result.

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Declarations

Funding

We had no financial declaration.

Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

There was no conflict of interest and the study was self-funded.

Code availability

Not available

Authors' Contributions

FDH & KA were involved in the study conception and design, FDH, HA, &HA were involved in the data collection and analysis, AO in data analysis,

FDH, MB & TO in the interpretation of results and all authors were involved in manuscript preparation.

Ethics approval

The patients' confidentiality and Helsinki declaration were respected in the conduct of this work.

Consent to participate

Not required

Consent for publication

Not required. The study was conducted strictly within the Ethical framework.

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